

HARDNESS EVALUATION "SHORE C" IN PLASTER MORTARS MADE WITH THE INCORPORATION OF DIFFERENT RESIDUE CONTENTS OF STONE POWDER.

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ABSTRACT

Hardness tests are widely used in the industry and can serve as an approximation of the rupture stress value. Shore C Hardness was performed in 84 specimens in which stone dust residues were incorporated into the plaster replacing gypsum in percentages of 10% to 50%. The results show a direct correlation between the observed data and the variables in the study: the hardness increases when the water/gypsum ratio decreases; and the hardness increases when the amount of gypsum replacement by stone powder increases.

KEY-WORDS Dynamic Tests; Shore Hardness C; Construction; Waste.

INTRODUCTION

Technological development associated with population growth and its consumption demand have generated the disorderly exploitation of non-renewable resources, increased energy consumption and producing a large volume of urban and industrial waste. This scenario has become a frequent theme around the world and induces the opening of a universe with new laws, research and investments in an attempt to minimize the negative impact that has been caused on the environment (THUNDER., 2012).

Civil construction represents a universe of problems and solutions in this scenario. It is an impacting agent due to the high consumption of raw materials and energy, and because it is a great waste generator. On the other hand, the sector has a great potential for the use of waste from various sectors, in addition to its socioeconomic importance (TROVÃO.,2012).

Currently, the Construction industry is seen as one of the most important strategic points for the Brazilian economy, since it is responsible for a significant portion of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). According to data from the Federation of Industries of the Federal District, civil construction accounts for 6.2% of the national GDP. In addition, it has 176,000 establishments, representing 34% of the industry. According to Teixeira e Carvalho (2005), the construction production chain has an intensive labor force, low import rate and high multiplier effects on the economy, concerning income, employment and taxes collected. Thus, the importance of the sector translates into a relevant consumption of materials and supplies, in quantity and diversity that, consequently, generate many wastes, resulting from an inefficient management of production processes.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay greater attention to the proper disposal of the remaining materials, as well as the increase of efforts in measures that reduce this generation directly at the source (SOUZA et al, 2004), thus seeking the use of new components that allow civil construction to work in a sustainable way.

The need to adapt the construction industry to the new model of world economic development,

where the search for sustainability of the sector is unquestionable, requires an interactive analysis of its entire production chain, consisting of different industrial segments, which provide the necessary supplies for civil construction. Among them can be mentioned the segments of the steel industry, the cement industry, the management industry, among others. In general, its activities begin with the extraction of natural resources and move to the processing of materials and the application of the material in the construction itself (KURESKI, et al., 2008).

The sustainable development of the chain depends on the sustainability of each segment, whose main elements to be controlled, are: (i) the reduction of the use of natural resources; (ii) the reduction of energy consumption; (iii) the reduction of waste generation; (iv) reuse and recycling, among others (DEGANI., 2003).

Awareness of the environmental problems faced in the modern world leads to the search for products and services developed through construction and industrial processes aimed at a clean consumption of natural resources. It is necessary to adapt to an economic development model capable of meeting current needs, without compromising future needs.

The environmental issue is increasingly being debated at the international, national and local spheres. Population growth and progress in industry and urbanization contribute to increased waste generation. Thus, the development, in the construction sector, causes increased consumption of energy and raw materials and leads to the generation of waste, causing an impact on the environment.

According to John (2000), the environmental impact of civil construction is proportional to its social task. It is through waste recycling that civil construction stands out as a major recycler of the economy.

The sector has a great prospect of growth in the context of recycling, due to the immense amount of materials it consumes and vast diversity in the composition of the materials it manufactures, and also for permeate throughout all regions (JOHN, 2000).

One of the materials that can certainly contribute to the improvement of the production processes of civil construction is the plaster in which with appropriate studies and technologies we can make the incorporation of waste in the pastes produced by this material. Knowing that the main properties of materials used in the area of civil construction are: hardness, compressive strength, bending strength and impact resistance and that according to Budynas and Nisbett (2011), the resistance of a material to the penetration of a pointed tool is known by hardness.

For the determination of hardness according to Dias (2004), among the varied mechanical tests that exist, the techniques of indentation have been showing themselves as one of the best options to determine the mechanical properties of materials with peculiar characteristics.

The indentation tests consist of the slow compression of a spherical or pyramidal penetrator of a rigid material on a flat surface, almost always polished and clean, of a sample to be analyzed, by a given load and during a certain time interval (DIAS, 2004). This compression will result in a permanent impression on the surface of the sample in the shape of the indentator.

There are several scales used in materials with different properties. The most common are A and D, A being used in soft plastics and D in rigid plastics. However, ASTM D 2240 contains 12 scales, dependent on intent to use, which are: A, B, C, D, DO, E, M, O, OO, OOO, OOO-S and R. Each scale results in a value between 0 and 100, with larger values indicating a harder material. In this work, shore C hardness was used, since it is indicated for materials such as rubbers and plastics of medium hardness and gypsum plaster.

In view of the above, this work aims to present an environmentally sustainable solution to be used in civil construction, using waste stone powder incorporated in gypsum matrix. This solution is based on the encapsulation of stone powder from the crushing of granite rocks in the gypsum paste,

giving a composite material to be used as blocks in structural masonry.

To verify the efficiency of this substitution, the effect of this incorporation of stone powder on the hardness of the specimens was studied.

The incorporation content of stone powder was 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% replacing gypsum mass. Gypsum water factors (w/w) ranging from 0.9, 0.8, 0.7, 0.6, 0.5 were used in order to analyze which trait offers the best performance characteristics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials that were the object of study of this work were water, commercial gypsum and granitic stone powder.

Water

All water used for the preparation of the pastes, cleaning of equipment, devices or other purposes was provided by the local concessionaire (CAGEPA), considered drinking and proper for use in construction activities.

Gypsum

The gypsum used in the experimental tests was commercial one, according Brazilian Standard ABNT NBR 13867 (ABNT, 1997). It is the most used in the city of Cajazeiras - PB and surroundings, where this work was done..

Powder stone

The stone powder was acquired in the CAJABRITA crusher also located in the city of Cajazeiras – PB. After its acquisition all the material used in the research was sieved in the sieve n. 4.8. The retained material was not utilized.

Methods

Cubic specimens of 50 mm x 50 mm x 50 mm, according to French Standard (AFNOR-CENT/TC241, 1991) were casted. Two series of three specimens for each condition were studied.

Experimental planning

In a first stage, plaster specimens called control were prepared. They were casted with water/gypsum ration (w/g) equal to 0.5, 0.6, 0.7 0.8 and 0.9 without the addition of stone powder. Then, using each w/g, the gypsum was replaced by 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% of stone powder, by mass. So, thirty combination were used.

Mixture

The tests were carried out at room temperature of approximately 30°C. The mixture was carried out in a plastic container. Water was put in the container and then the gypsum was sprayed for 1 minute, leaving it to rest for 2 minutes. Then mix was done for 1 minute and the material put in the cubic moulds.

In mixtures with w/g = 0.5 and 40 % and 50% of stone powder it was not possible to perform the tests since the mixtures did not acquire any plasticity.

Moulding

For each mixture, three cubic specimens of 50.0 mm of the border were molded simultaneously in a rigid waterproof mold, non-reactive to calcium sulfate. After demolding, all specimens had their edges measured, confirming that there was no retraction and identified on the shallow face.

Surface hardness test

Hardness as well as penetration resistance or risk for the characterization of solid hardness is usually used. In the Shore test, a durometer measures the resistance, taken as the measure of hardness, to the penetration of a pin pressed against the rigid surface by the action of a spring under standardized load, Figure 1. A pointer moves across a scale to show penetration resistance, and the scales on the Shore Durometer range from 0 to 100, the Shore Scale

Three specimens were tested for each type of composite, and the mean was obtained.

Figure 1: Hardness test using the Shore C durometer.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the graphical data of the effect of the different stone powder substitution contents used in this research on the Shore C Hardness specimens with $w/g = 0.9$

Figure 2: Effect of the different stone powder substitution contents on the Shore C Hardness on specimens with $w/g = 0.9$

It can be noticed that there is a tendency of increase in hardness shore C in the specimens with the increase of the content of stone powder. Comparing the specimens with 50% replacement content with the control specimens, there was an increase in hardness by 11 %.

The specimens with a replacement content of 20% was that least contributed to the increase in hardness, being almost equal to control.

When the substitution percentages go from 30 to 50% the hardness value practically does not change.

Figure 3 shows the results of the effect of the different stone powder substitution contents used in the shore C hardness of the molded specimens with $w/g = 0,8$

Figure 3: Effect of the different contents of stone powder substitution on the shore hardness C specimens with $w/g = 0.8$.

The chart above shows that the trend of increases in hardness with the increase of substitution remains, more with less relevant effects. When analyzing the values obtained in the control mixture with respect to the mixture with 50% substitution, we verified that this increase produced an increase in hardness of 1.35%

We also observed that the replacement content with the most significant result in the improvement of this magnitude was 30% which led to an increase in hardness of 1.67%

The replacement content of 20% produced virtually no significant effects on hardness.

By increasing the replacement levels from 30% to 40 and 50% a low decrease in the hardness of the material can be seen.

Figure 4 shows the effect of the different stone powder substitution contents used in this research on the Shore C hardness of the specimens with $w/g=0.7$. When analyzing the data in Figure 4, we noticed an interesting effect, the growth trend of the hardness in the mixtures with the increase of substitution is reversed. The increase in substitution causes a tendency to decrease the hardness of the specimens, this trend becomes evident when we compared the results obtained in the control and the specimens with 50% replacement where there was a decrease of 1.73% in hardness.

When the mix with 30% replacement is compared with that using 50% replacement, there is a drop of 1.55%.

The only trait that produced a positive effect on the hardness gain was the 10% substitution but the gain of 0.51% is almost irrelevant.

Figure 4: Effect of the different contents of stone powder substitution on the shore hardness C specimens with $w/g = 0.7$.

Figure 5: Effect of the different contents of stone powder substitution on the shore hardness C specimens with $w/g = 0.6$.

In Figure 5 it is shown the results concerning $w/g = 0.6$. The trend of decreased shore C hardness with the increase of substitution is more visible. Unlike the series with $w/g = 0.7$ in which with the substitution of 10% it is still possible to verify an improvement in this property, in the now all mixtures presented values lower than the control.

Comparing the control mixture with that using 40% replacement of gypsum by stone powder a decrease of 3.71% in hardness was found.

Although this downward trend in shore hardness is clear, in percentage terms it is small which would not produce any significant practical effect.

When comparing the mixtures with 10% and 30% of substitution we noticed that this increase produces a reduction of only 2 %

Figure 6 shows the graph with the results of the series hardness tests with $w/g = 0.5$

Figure 6: Effect of the different contents of stone powder substitution on the shore hardness C specimens with w/g = 0.5.

Regarding the data obtained in this series, it was not possible to reach clear conclusions, due the discrepancy in the data obtained. This because the mixtures of this series had little or no plasticity, which resulted in folders that were difficult to mold, resulting in no perfect specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

For the series with w/g = 0.9 it was found that:

In all substitution levels there was an increase in the surface hardness of the specimens.

When comparing the specimens with replacement content of 50% with the control there was an increase in hardness by 11 %.

The specimens with substitution content of 20% were the ones that least contributed to the increase in hardness, but still exceeded the control trait, producing an increase in this magnitude of 0.67%.

When the substitution percentages changes from 30 to 50% the hardness value practically does not change increasing 0.42%

For the series with factor (w/w) 0.8 it was found that:

The trend of increase in hardness with the increase of substitution not only remained but increased.

The values obtained in the control mixture with respect to the mixture with 50% replacement provided an increase in hardness of 1.35%

The replacement content with the most significant result in the improvement was 30% which led to an increase in hardness of 1.67%.

The replacement content of 20% produced virtually no significant effects on hardness.

For the series with w/g = 0.7 it was found that:

The growth trend of shore C hardness in mixtures with the increase of substitution is reversed.

The specimens with 50% replacement caused a decrease of 1.73% in the hardness of the material when compared to the control specimens.

The only mixture that produced a positive effect on the hardness gain was the 10% substitution trait that provided the almost irrelevant gain of 0.51%

For the series with factor (w/w) 0.6 it was found that:

The tendency of decreased hardness of shore C with the increase of substitution not only remained but augmented.

Unlike the series with w/g = 0.7 in which with the substitution of 10% it is still possible to verify an improvement in this property, in the series with w/g = 0.6 all mixtures resulted in values lower than those obtained in relation to the control mixture.

The mixture with 40% replacement of gypsum by stone powder produced a decrease of 3.71% in hardness.

Although this downward trend in shore hardness is clear, in percentage terms it is small which would not produce any significant practical effect.

For the series with w/g = 0.5 it was found that:

Due to the poor quality of the specimens obtained, no reliable results were found.

In view of the data presented, it is generally verified that there is an increase in shore C hardness when the value of the gypsum replacement percentile by stone powder is increased. There is also an addition of this property when the water/plaster ratio decreases. Thus specimens with higher replacement content and lower water/gypsum ratio result in materials with better qualities in relation to this property.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.